

A STUDY ON FRACTURE MECHANISMS OF CLASS-A SMC
BY ACOUSTIC EMISSION METHOD

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ABSTRACT

The AE method is applied to a class-A SMC composite material that is a sheet molding compound composite material having the excellent surface smoothness. Analyzing some kinds of AE parameters, it is discussed here how the fracture processes of the class A-SMC composite material are affected by the constituent factors such as the resin, the calcium carbonate and the glass fiber.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, sheet molding compound (SMC) composite materials have been widely used for exterior parts of automobiles. But the conventional SMC composite materials have the wavy and undulated patterns which appear on the molded surfaces due to the shrinkage during the cooling process after being released from the mold.

Due to the developments in the low shrinkage resin and the techniques of high filling up of the calcium carbonates and lowering the unevenness of the distribution of the glass fibers, the new SMC has been developed so that it has excellent surface smoothness and can be used for the automobile exterior parts with so-called class A surfaces. So, the new SMC is named "class A-SMC" and can be utilized in making the front hoods, doors, roofs and the other main exterior parts of automobiles [1].

The AE (acoustic emission) method has been used to investigate the deformation and fracture mechanisms. The fracture mechanisms of composite materials are very complicated because the process includes the matrix fracture, the debonding between the matrix and the fiber, the fiber breaking, the delamination and so forth [2]. Therefore, the AE wave contains so many kinds of information that there are many problems for applying the method to composite materials. However, it is considered that the application is made possible by analyzing various kinds of AE parameters. In this paper, applying the AE method to the class A-SMC composite material it is discussed how the fracture processes of the material are affected by the constituent factors such as the resin, the calcium carbonate and the glass fiber.

EXPERIMENTS

Test Materials

The low shrinkage resin compound in the class-A SMC used here is an unsaturated polyester where the saturated polyester is mixed as the plasticizer. In this resin compound, the calcium carbonate is filled up and the short glass fibers (the diameter of 13 μ m and the length of about 25mm) are dispersed in strands containing 200-400 fibers. In the material, the ratio of resin to calcium carbonate is 100 to 180 and the fiber content is 30% in weight.

In order to investigate how the constituent factors affect the fracture mechanisms of the class A-SMC composite material, four kinds of materials are prepared: the resin only, the calcium carbonate plus the resin, the glass fiber plus the resin, and the class A-SMC. These materials are named here A, B, C, and D, respectively. The mechanical properties of these materials are shown in Table 1.

The experiments are done with the CT specimens machined from these materials. The SEN specimens are also prepared for the material D. The geometries and the dimensions of these specimens are shown in Figure 1.

Test Methods

The experiments are done at the room temperature by using an Instron type testing machine (Shimadzu, Autograph IS-10T) at the crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. The load P and the crack opening displacement V are recorded on an X-Y recorder. The AE signals are detected by an AE measuring apparatus (Shimadzu, SAE 1000A) under the condition that the total gain of the amplifiers is 60 dB and the threshold voltage is 0.3 mVo-p. The signals with the frequency lower than 10 kHz are removed by a high pass filter to remove noises. The AE parameters obtained by this measuring apparatus are the cumulative event count, the AE event count rate, the total AE energy and the AE amplitude distribution. The power spectrum is also obtained by inputting the AE signals recorded on the data recorder (Sony Magnescale, FMR 1219) into a wave form analyzer (Analogic, DATA 6000). The schematic of this AE measuring system is shown in Figure 2. Two types of sensors are used; the one is a resonance type whose resonance frequency is about 200-400 kHz and the another is a wide range type which can detect the wave with the frequency of up to 1MHz. The AE signals detected by the former are used for obtaining the AE parameters and the signals by the latter are used

TABLE 1
Mechanical properties of materials

Material	Elastic modulus E (GPa)	Tensile strength σ_B (MPa)	Poisson's ratio ν	Elongation ϕ (%)
A	3.0	20	0.4	2.9
B	9.7	27	0.3	1.7
C	10.5	108	0.3	8.6
D	15.2	73	0.3	6.9

(a) CT specimen.

(b) SEN specimen.

Figure 1. Shape and dimension of test specimens.

Figure 2. Block diagram for measuring AE.

for the frequency analysis. The sensors are used in two channels to avoid noise and are attached to the test specimens with an adhesive agent carefully and tightly at a position as shown in Figure 2. The micro-fracture surface is also observed by a scanning electron microscope.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Load-Displacement Curve, AE Energy and AE Event Count Rate

Figure 3 shows the total AE energy and the AE event count rate as well as the load - crack opening displacement (P-V) curve. The total AE energy shown by the dotted line is the cumulative value of the energy obtained as a square of the peak amplitude of the AE wave. The P-V curves of the materials A and B are linear up to the maximum load points where the specimens fracture. The AE events are found to be a few in these materials. The P-V curve of C and D materials are linear in the initial stage and

Figure 3. Load - crack opening displacement curve, AE event count rate and total AE energy.

represent non-linear behaviors from the points shown by the arrows. The loads at those points are 50 and 60% of the maximum loads for the materials C and D, respectively. The AE event count rate and the AE energy increase from those points and the former decreases after passing the maximum loads. The comparison of Figures 3 (c) and (d) with Figures (a) and (b) suggests that the AE generations are affected remarkably by the contained glass fibers.

Relation Between AE Amplitude Distribution and Constituent Factors of Materials

Figure 4 shows the distributions of the peak amplitudes of AE events from the beginning of loading to the neighborhoods of the maximum loads for the CT specimens. In the materials A and B where a few event appears, the amplitude is lower than 2 mVo-p. In the materials C and D where many AE events appear, the amplitudes are widely distributed. The amplitude ranges containing many events are from 0.5 to 4 mVo-p for the material C and are from 1 to 3 mVo-p and 6 to 7 mVo-p for D. It is considered that the AE events with low AE amplitudes found in the material A correspond to the fractures of the resin. Figure 5 shows the microfractograph of the material B which is made of the resin and the calcium carbonate. It is found that there are the debonded or fractured particles of the calcium carbonate. Therefore, it is considered that the AE event detected in B corresponds to the fracture of the particle or the debonding between the resin and the particle. The AE events in the materials C and D are considered to correspond to the fiber debonding, the fiber pulling out and the fiber breaking, since few events appear in the materials A and B. In order to investigate the effects of the fibers, the microfractograph of the material D is shown in Figure 6. It is observed that there are many fibers which

Figure 4. AE amplitude distribution to the maximum load for CT specimen.

Figure 5. Microfractograph of material B.

(a) Pulled-out fibers.

(b) Broken fibers.

Figure 6. Microfractograph of material D.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 7. AE amplitude distribution by a parameter of AE energy for CT specimen of material D.

were pulled out or broken, and also that the number of pulled out fibers are more than the broken ones. Therefore it is considered that the AE event with the lower amplitude corresponds to the debonding and the pulling out of the fiber, and the event with higher amplitude corresponds to the breaking of the fiber. Generally, the amplitude of the AE event due to the fiber breaking is higher than one due to the fiber pulling out [3], which coincides with this result.

Figure 7 shows the AE amplitude distributions for the material D in four periods : (a) near the point of the beginning of the AE generation, (b) before the point of a rapid increase of AE energies, (c) near this point and (d) after this point. It is found that the AE events in the period (a) have the lower amplitude (lower than 2 mVo-p) and the events in (b) have the medium amplitude (2-4 mVo-p) as well as the lower one. The

Figure 8. AE amplitude distribution to the final fracture for SEN specimen of material D.

Figure 9. AE amplitude distribution by a parameter of AE energy for SEN specimen of material D.

events with the higher amplitude (higher than 6 mVo-p) begin to appear in (c) and increase in (d). Therefore, it is considered that the CT specimen of the class A-SMC fractures in the following process : at the beginning the resin and the particles of the calcium carbonate fracture and the interfaces between the resin and the particles debond, next the interfaces between the matrix and the fibers debond and the fibers are pulled out, finally the fibers break.

Figure 8 shows the AE amplitude distribution from the beginning to the final fracture of the SEN specimen for the material D. This figure differs a little from Figure 4(d) for the CT specimen. In order to investigate more precisely this difference, the AE amplitude distributions in the four periods similar to those for the CT specimen are shown in Figure 9. In the period (a), the amplitudes are from about 2 to 4 mVo-p, which is higher than ones in the CT specimen. In the periods (b) and (c), events with amplitudes of from about 3 to 4 mVo-p are contained which do not appear in the CT specimen. In the period (d) there are much more events than ones in CT and many events appear in the amplitude range of from 2 to 6 mVo-p. In the period (b), the surface cracking appears at the notch tip in the SEN specimen as shown in Figure 10. The cracking has been caused by the delamination between the surface layer and the interior. Also the delaminations between the inner layers are found on the macroscopic fracture surface of the SEN specimen as shown in Figure 11. Therefore the events with amplitudes of from 2 to 6 mVo-p are caused by these delaminations.

Relation Between Frequency Distribution and Constituent Factors of Materials

Since the AE amplitude is affected by the position of the sensor, it's numerical value has only a relative meaning. In this section, therefore, the fracture mechanisms are studied by the power spectra of the AE wave. Figure 12 shows the examples of the power spectra at the typical points from the beginning to the maximum of the load of the CT specimens for the four kinds of materials. In the material A, the components of the power spectrum are distributed in the range from 80 to 180 kHz and the peak of the power is at 150 kHz. For the material B, the components are distributed in the ranges from 80 to 200 kHz and from 240 to 450 kHz where the peaks appear at 150 kHz and 310 kHz. These results show that the AE events in the frequency range of from 80 to 180 kHz are generated by the cracking of the resin and ones in the range of from 240 to 450 kHz are generated by the debonding between the resin and the particles of the

Figure 10. Macroscopic observation of surface cracking.

Figure 11. Macroscopic observation of delamination.

calcium carbonate as well as the cracking of the particles. The frequency ranges in the material C are divided to three ranges, of from 80 to 180 kHz, from 180 to 250 kHz and from 250 to 400 kHz, where the peaks are at 50, 190 and 310 kHz, respectively. The peak in the range of from 250 to 400 kHz is higher than one in the range of from 180 to 250 kHz. In the material D, the components are distributed in the range of from 80 to 400 kHz and the peaks appear at 150, 190, 270 and 310 kHz. From these results and the consideration of the amplitude distribution in the previous section it is found that the AE events in the range of from 180 to 250 kHz are due to the fiber pulling out as well as the debonding between the matrix and

Figure 12. An example of relation between power spectrum and frequency to the maximum load for CT specimen.

Figure 13. Classification of AE source by frequency analysis.

the fiber, and ones in the range of from 250 to 450 kHz are due to the fiber breaking. Thus the AE generation sources are classified by the frequency as shown in Figure 13. It seems that the AE generation sources are easily discriminated by this result.

CONCLUSIONS

Applying the AE method to a class A-SMC composite material which is developed for the outer panels of automobiles, the relations between the AE parameters and the fracture mechanisms have been studied in this paper. The results obtained are as follows.

(1) The measurements of the AE amplitudes and the observations of the fracture surfaces have shown the following relations between the AE amplitude and the fracture mechanisms. The amplitude of the resin fracture is very low. The AE amplitude of the fracture of the particle of the calcium carbonate and the debonding between the resin and the particle are also low, but these are higher than the ones by the resin fracture. The sources of the AE wave with the higher amplitude are the fiber debonding and pulling out, the delamination and the fiber breaking in the order of the height of the amplitude.

(2) The fracture mechanisms have been studied also by a frequency analysis of the AE wave using a power spectrum as the spectrum parameter. From these results and the considerations of the amplitude, it has been found that the frequency ranges of AE waves corresponding to the resin cracking, the debonding between the resin and the particle of the calcium carbonate as well as the particle cracking, the debonding between the matrix and the fiber as well as the fiber pulling out, and the fiber breaking are 80-180, 240-450, 180-250, and 250-450 kHz, respectively.

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